

ORGANISATIONAL CLIMATE AND COMMITMENT: A SARAWAK VOCATIONAL COLLEGES' TEACHERS PERSPECTIVE

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study was to examine the relationship of organisational climate and commitment from the perspective of vocational colleges' teachers in Sarawak, Malaysia. A total of six vocational colleges involving 691 teachers participated in this study. The Organisational Climate Index (OCI) and Organisational Commitment Questionnaire (OCQ) were used in measuring the relationship between the four dimensions in organisational climate, namely, collegial leadership, professional teacher behaviour, achievement press and institutional vulnerability and the teachers' organisational commitment. The results of the statistical analysis indicated collegial leadership, professional teacher behaviour and achievement press showed significant positive relationships with teachers' organisational commitment. However, institutional vulnerability was found to have no significant relationship with teachers' organisational commitment. The multiple regression analysis revealed that the best predictor of teachers' organisational commitment was professional teacher behaviour. Collegial leadership and achievement press were also found to be good predictors of teachers' organisational commitment. This study contributed in enhancing a better understanding of the relationship between the organisational climate and teachers' organisational

commitment. Several recommendations were made for future research interests.

Keywords: Organisational climate, organisational commitment, vocational colleges' teachers, Sarawak.

INTRODUCTION

Organisational climate has been a popular theme in educational management research for the past few decades. Potentially, it affects a range of organisational and individual desired outcomes inclusive of commitment, loyalty, turnover intention and job satisfaction (Akoto & Allida, 2017; Hosseini & Talebian Nia, 2015; Douglas, 2010; MacNeil, Prater & Busch, 2009; Meyer & Allen, 1997; Kottkamp, Mulhern & Hoy, 1987). Scholars presume that organisational climate influences teachers' sense of engagement, identification and belonging (Bahramia, Barati, Ghoroghchian, Al-Faraj & Ezzatabadi, 2016; Othman & Kasuma, 2016; Smith, 2009; Dee, Henkin & Singleton, 2006; Hoy, Smith & Sweetland, 2002). Such sentiments might reasonably be expected to impact on their commitment (Chung, 2014). In Malaysia, The Ministry of Education (MOE) is aware that the development of a nation, unity and economic growth are two important aspects towards transforming Malaysia as high-revenue nation. To ensure that our generation is ready to compete at global level and able to maintain success, The Malaysian Education Blueprint 2006-2010 and the Malaysian Education Blueprint 2013-2025 were introduced in 2006 and 2013 respectively (MOE, 2019). The Blueprint stated that education plays an important role in developing human capital who are knowledgeable and competent, who possess high moral standards, responsible and capable of achieving high levels of personal well-being as well as able to contribute to the harmony and betterment of the family, society and nation at large so as to fulfill the needs for the 2020 nation (MOE, 2019). This shows that education is an important tool towards producing quality human capital who will make the nation's vision a reality. To ensure the effectiveness of education provided towards this direction, the vocational colleges (formerly known as

technical school) were established. For instance, currently, there are six vocational colleges with 4555 students and 698 teachers in Sarawak which is the largest state in Malaysia (MOE, 2019).

If the school is deemed the agent of change towards producing quality human capital for the nation, then, school climate is an essential factor that influences the change (Raman, Chang & Khalid, 2015). In this context, the school climate affects the teachers' commitment towards their organisation. However, the lack of research attention given to the effect of organisational climate on teacher's commitment in previous studies highlights a significant research gap that requires further investigation. Specifically, the relationships between the four dimensions of organisational climate, namely, collegial leadership, professional teacher behaviour, achievement press and institutional vulnerability and teacher's commitment are largely unexplored neither in Malaysia nor in Sarawak. Therefore, this study can further clarify and add into the literature on organisational climate and teacher's commitment, hence, aiding educational administrators in particular, a better understanding of their organisation's climate and commitment.

Purpose of the Study

This study aims to determine the relationship between organisational climate and commitment from the perspective of vocational colleges' teachers in Sarawak, Malaysia.

Research Questions

1. What is the level of organisational commitment of the teachers from the vocational colleges in Sarawak?
2. What is the level of organisational climate of the vocational colleges in Sarawak?
3. What is the relationship between the organisational climate (collegial leadership, professional teacher behaviour, achievement press and institutional vulnerability) and teacher's organisational commitment?

4. What is/are the dominant predictor factor/s of organisational climate on teacher's organisational commitment?

Hypotheses

H₁: Collegial leadership is positively correlated with teacher's organisational commitment.

H₂: Professional teacher behaviour is positively correlated with teacher's organisational commitment.

H₃: Achievement press is positively correlated with teacher's organisational commitment.

H₄: Institutional vulnerability is negatively correlated with teacher's organisational commitment.

H₅: Professional teacher behaviour is the only predictor on teacher's organisational commitment.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The study of school climate is rooted in the work of Halpin and Croft as early as in 1962 (Halpin & Croft, 1963). They referred the organization climate of a school as the school's personality and each school has its unique climate or personality. Hoy, Tarter and Kootkamp (1991) stated that school climate is the quality of the school surrounding or the school environment that is familiarized by the members of the school. These characteristics differentiate one school from another and affect the behaviour of the members of the school. Hoy and Hoy (2006) drew the conclusion that school climate is directly related to school outcomes. The intention of study school climate was originated by two separate frameworks, namely, the openness and health for the analysis and measurement of school climate.

Douglas (2010), argued that Halpin and Croft were the pioneers in the study of openness of school climate. Halpin and Croft (1963) devised the Organisational Climate Description Questionnaire (OCDQ) to measure school climate. The determination of openness was dependent upon teacher's perceptions of the organisation. These perceptions were based on the interpersonal relationship among teachers and their relationship with the principal. The OCDQ places the school along a continuum of open to close. In the later research conducted by Hoy (2013), described the open climate as supportive, authentic and most likely to bring about organisational change. On one hand, teachers working in an open climate are more likely to go for the extra mile and work for organisational success. On the other hand, those who are working in the close climate is described as hostile, closed and most likely to fail in terms of organisational improvement.

The study of health of school climate is rooted in the works of Miles and Parsons in 1969 (Akoto & Allida, 2017; Lucero & Etom, 2017; Hoy, 2013). In a healthy school, the teachers are committed, work well together and set high but attainable goals for students. The students are motivated and they respect the achievement of other students. On the contrary, an unhealthy school is susceptible to outside factors such as parents and community. The principal is ineffective and gives less support for teachers. As a result, the teachers are not committed neither to their work nor the organisation. They generally exhibit very low morale and are mistrustful of the administration. Based on these studies, in 1987, Hoy and Feldman were able to formulate the Organisational Health Inventory (OHI) to measure the health of schools (Hoy & Miskel, 2013).

The concept of a healthy school is similar in context to that of an open school. The conceptual overlaps of openness and health led to the formation of the Organisational Climate Index (OCI) (Hoy, Smith & Sweetland, 2002; Hoy & Sabo, 1998). The four dimensions of the OCI are: institutional vulnerability, collegial leadership, professional teacher behaviour and achievement press. The OCI and its four dimensions serve

as key component to this study of the relationship between climate and commitment.

Along with climate, commitment is another important variable of organisational research. Commitment emphasizes on attachment or desire to remain with the organisation, willingness towards exerting extra effort and sharing organisation's goals and values. Commitment goes beyond loyalty to an organisation. It involves giving of one's self to the organisation with a spirit of "go an extra mile" for the organisation (Smith, 2009; Reihl & Sipple, 1996).

Arguably, the characteristics of a school influence teacher commitment. For instance, teachers receiving support from their superior are more likely to be committed to the school's goals and values. Teachers working in an orderly school have a higher level of desire to remain with the organisation. Similarly, classroom autonomy for teachers is another characteristic associated with commitment. Peer support is also a key element in teacher commitment (Raman, Chang & Khalid, 2015; Chung, 2014; Smith, 2009).

Therefore, conceptually organisational climate is associated with commitment. Hence, this study can contribute to explain the relationship between these two variables.

Collegial Leadership and Commitment

Conceptually, any principal that treats teachers as colleagues, is open to their opinions, establishes high and achievable standards of performance, and is friendly and courteous. All these elements should enhance some level of teacher's commitment (Douglas, 2010). Previous research, (Lucero & Etom, 2017; Raman, Chang, & Khalid, 2015; Ebrahimi, & Mohamadkhani, 2014) supported this conceptual link and found that a significant positive relationship between supportive principal or collegial leadership and teacher's organisational commitment. Hence, a positive relationship between these two variables is expected.

Professional Teacher Behaviour and Commitment

In a school setting that its climate demonstrates the teachers' support and respect for each other, committed to students' achievement and beliefs in each other's abilities should outline some level of teacher's organisational commitment. Previous studies such as Lucero and Etom (2017), Hosseini and Talebian (2015), Ebrahimi and Mohamadkhani (2014) and Smith (2009) supported a strong relationship between professional teacher behaviour and teacher's organisational commitment. Another group of researchers (Bahramia, et. al., 2016; Othman & Kasuma, 2016; Smith, 2009) found that professional teacher behaviour was the only predictor for commitment.

Achievement Press and Commitment

Scholars believe that a school climate where high and achievable academic standards are set, all stakeholders press for high achievement and students work hard to achieve and gain teachers respect might expect some level of teacher's organisational commitment. Previous studies by Othman & Kasuma (2016); Raman, Chang and Khalid (2015) and Savas and Toprak (2014) supported the strong positive relationship between achievement press and student achievement and effect on teacher's organisational commitment.

Institutional Vulnerability and Commitment

A school with a vulnerable climate is susceptible to outside forces and resulting a low level of teacher's organisational commitment. This type of school climate will leave the teachers and principal unprotected from influential parents and citizen groups. Despite a suspected significant relationship, previous researches by Akoto and Allida (2017); Hosseini and Talebian Nia (2015); Reza, Jafar, Mohammad, Hasan and Shahrookh (2013) and Smith (2009) had failed to support this conceptual link.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Descriptive and inferential research designs were used in this study. Documentary analysis was executed in order to understand the theories and studies concerning the organisational climate and teacher's organisational commitment. This study made use of two types of questionnaires, namely, Organisational Climate Index (OCI) and Organisational Commitment Questionnaire (OCQ) to collect data from the subjects exclusively from the vocational colleges in Sarawak, Malaysia. The original OCQ established by Mowday, Steers and Porter (1979) was a 15-item questionnaire that measured the degree of involvement respondents have in their organisation. However, in this study, the 9-item version was used due to the suggestion made from the reliability test in which those six items with the Cronbach's Alpha coefficients lesser than 0.70 were consequently deleted. The teachers responded to those items along with a 5-point Likert scale ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree.

In order to examine its reliability and construct validity, a pilot study for the drafted questionnaire was carried out. The results of the pilot study revealed that the Cronbach's Alpha coefficients for all four dimensions in OCI were relatively high: institutional vulnerability (0.90), collegial leadership (0.91), professional teacher behaviour (0.88) and achievement press (0.91). The Cronbach's Alpha coefficients for OCQ ranged from 0.65 to 0.90. Six items that scored lesser than 0.70 were deleted to make the overall reading of Cronbach's Alpha coefficients to settle at 0.86 which showed a high degree of reliability. Item analysis also been conducted. The results revealed that all the items from these two sets of questionnaires reached the significant level at 0.05. Furthermore, the results of factor analysis also showed adequate construct validity.

The population of this study consists of all 698 teachers from the vocational colleges in Sarawak (MOE, 2019). By using stratified random sampling, the population were separated into two stratum in accordance with gender. The questionnaires were sent to all 698 teachers in the

population. As a result, 695 of the teachers responded. However, only 691 or 99.4% were useful responses. All data collected were analysed using SPSS version 21.

RESULT

Respondents' Profile

Table 1: Demographic Profile of Respondents

Factor	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	291	42.1%
	Female	400	57.9%
Age	21-30	135	19.5%
	31-40	277	40.1%
	41-50	162	23.4%
	51-60	117	17.0%
	Marital status	Married	556
	Single	135	19.5%
Length of Service	1-10 years	131	18.9%
	11-20 years	318	46.0%
	21-30 years	177	25.7%
	> 30 years	65	9.4%
Location	Urban	431	62.4%
	Rural	260	37.6%

The descriptive analysis of the sample was performed for gender, age, marital status, length of service and location with the current vocational colleges as shown in Table 1. The results showed that gender distribution favoured to the female teachers (400, 57.9%) in comparison with male teachers (291, 42.1%). Majority of the teachers (277, 40.1%) aged between 31 to 40 years old, followed by those in 41-50 years age group (162, 23.4%). 135 (19.5%) teachers aged 21 to 30 years old, while the remaining 65 (17%) teachers aged 51 to 60 years old. Majority of the teachers (556, 80.5%) stated they are married and only 135 (19.5%) of them still single. The length of service of the teachers in the teaching profession revealed that majority of them (318, 46%) have been teaching for 11 to 20 years, 177 or 25.7% of them have been teaching for 21 to 30 years and 65 or 9.4% of them

have been servicing in the teaching profession for more than 30 years. The rest, 131 or 18.9% of the teachers indicated that they have been in the service for the first decade. The results also revealed that 431 (62.4%) teachers located at the urban vocational colleges. While, the other 260 (37.6%) teachers located at the rural vocational colleges.

Teachers’ Organisational Commitment Level in the Vocational Colleges in Sarawak

Research question 1:

What is the level of organisational commitment of the teachers from the vocational colleges in Sarawak?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation for Teacher’s Organisational Commitment

Aspect in Commitment	Mean (\bar{x})	Standard Deviation (SD)
Commitment towards exerting extra effort	4.15	0.51
Desire to remain with the organisation	4.20	0.48
Sharing the values and goals of the organisation	4.17	0.47
Overall	4.10	0.40

In order to address this question, the researcher used descriptive analysis to obtain the overall mean value for each aspect in commitment, followed by comparing the overall mean with mean interpretation to determine the level of teachers’ commitment. The findings from Table 2 showed that the Sarawakian vocational colleges teachers have an overall of high level of teacher’s organisational commitment ($\bar{x} = 4.10$). They demonstrated the highest level of commitment from the aspect of desire to remain with the organisation ($\bar{x} = 4.20$). This was followed by the aspect of sharing the values and goals of the organisation ($\bar{x} = 4.17$) and commitment towards exerting extra effort ($\bar{x} = 4.15$).

The high level of teachers' organisational commitment ($\bar{x} = 4.10$), is perceived to be one of the factors that affects the academic performance of the vocational colleges. The finding of this study confirms the conclusion made in previous studies by Othman and Kasuma (2016), Raman, Chang and Khalid (2015) and Najeemah (2012) that committed teachers having strong psychological bond with the school, students and their subjects. They believed that highly committed teachers will work hard and diligently to strive for excellent students' academic performance. This finding is also consistent with the finding by Raman, Chang and Khalid (2015) and Gupta and Gehlawat (2013) that organisational commitment is an important factor contributing to an effective education system. Teachers who are highly committed are more likely motivated with their work and they perform their teaching tasks voluntarily. Therefore, having a pool of highly committed teachers will be the key of success for the vocational colleges and the entire education system.

Organisational Climate level in the Vocational Colleges in Sarawak

Research question 2:

What is the level of organisational climate of the vocational colleges in Sarawak?

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation for Organisational Climate

Organisational Climate Dimension	Mean (\bar{x})	Standard Deviation (SD)
Collegial leadership	3.19	0.40
Professional teacher behaviour	3.47	0.46
Achievement press	3.29	0.50
Institutional vulnerability	2.14	0.80
Overall	3.12	0.35

Another descriptive analysis was conducted to ascertain the overall mean value for each climate dimension followed by comparing the overall mean

with mean interpretation to determine the level of organisational climate in the vocational colleges in Sarawak. The results shown in Table 3 revealed that moderately high mean values for all the dimensions; collegial leadership dimension ($\bar{x} = 3.19$), professional teacher behaviour ($\bar{x} = 3.47$), achievement press ($\bar{x} = 3.29$) and institutional vulnerability ($\bar{x} = 2.14$). The overall mean value of organisational climate for the six vocational colleges in Sarawak is 3.12. The results of this study concur with the findings from previous studies by Akoto and Allida (2017) and Hoy (2013) which found that high level of school climate in high schools.

Hypothesis Testing

The Relationship Between Organisational Climate and Teacher's Organisational Commitment

In this study, in order to measure the strength of the relationship between organisational climate and teacher commitment, the Table of Correlation Value Interpretation developed by Bartlett, Kontrlik, and Hinggins (2001) was referred.

Table 4: Correlation Value Interpretation

Correlation Value (r)	Relationship Strength
± 0.70 – 0.99	Very Strong
± 0.50 – 0.69	Strong
± 0.30 – 0.49	Moderately strong
± 0.10 – 0.29	Weak
± 0.01 – 0.09	Very weak

Research question 3:

What is the relationship between the organisational climate (collegial leadership, professional teacher behaviour, achievement press and institutional vulnerability) and teacher's organisational commitment?

Table 5: Correlations Between Organisational Climate and Teacher’s Organisational Commitment

Variable	Comm	CoL	PTB	AP	
IVul					
Commitment (Comm)		-			
Collegial leadership (CoL)	0.66**	-			
Professional teacher behaviour (PTB)	0.76**	0.56**	-		
Acheivement press (AP)	0.63**	0.43**	0.61**	-	
Institutional vulnerability (IVul)	-0.12	-0.08	-0.21	-0.03	-

***Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (One-tailed).*

Relationship between Collegial Leadship and Teacher’s Organisational Commitment

The results of the correlations analysis from Table 5 revealed that there is a significant, positive and strong relationship between collegial leadership and teacher commitment ($r = 0.66$, $n = 691$, $p < 0.01$). The positive significant relationship shows that an increase in collegial leadership dimension will increase the level of teachers’ commitment and vice versa. Therefore, H_1 : Collegial leadership is positively correlated with teacher’s organisational commitment is supported. The results are consistent with the theory that teachers will be committed to their organisation when they are led by a principal who practices positive collegial leadership and providing structure, resources, consideration, useful influence and professional support in a nonthreatening, noncontrolling manner (Douglas, 2010; Tarter, Hoy & Bliss, 1989). The results also supported previous findings by Lucero and Etom (2017), Othman and Kasuma (2016), Raman, Chang and Khalid (2015), Hosseini and Talebian Nia (2015), Ebrahimi and Mohamadkhani (2014).

Relationship between Professional Teacher Behaviour and Teacher's Organisational Commitment

The correlations analysis also showed a significant, positive and strong relationship between the professional teacher behaviour and commitment ($r = 0.76$, $n = 691$, $p < 0.01$). The positive significant relationship shows that an increase in professional teacher behaviour will increase the level of teacher's commitment as well. Therefore, H₂: Professional teacher behaviour is positively correlated with teacher's organisational commitment is supported. The results concur with the previous findings (Lucero & Etom, 2017; Hosseini & Talebian, 2015; Raman, Chang, & Khalid, 2015; Ebrahimi & Mohamadkhani, 2014; Smith, 2009). The results also support the notion that the relationship that teachers have with one another is more vital to teacher's organisational commitment than the relationship that a teacher has with his/her principal (Smith, 2009).

Relationship between Achievement Press and Teacher's Organisational Commitment

A similar relationship with the former two variables was found between achievement press and teacher's organisational commitment ($r = 0.63$, $n = 691$, $p < 0.01$). The positive significant relationship shows that any increase in achievement press dimension in school climate will increase the level of teacher's organisational commitment and vice versa. Therefore, H₃: Achievement press is positively correlated with teacher's organisational commitment is supported. The results confirm the findings from previous studies (Othman & Kasuma, 2016; Raman, Chang & Khalid, 2015; Savas & Toprak, 2014; Hoy & Miskel, 2008) and support the conceptual link between the two variables (Hoy, Smith & Sweetland, 2002; Hoy & Sabo, 1998).

Relationship between Institutional Vulnerability and Teacher’s Organisational Commitment

Surprisingly, institutional vulnerability was found to have no significant relationship with teacher’s organisational commitment ($r = -0.12$, $n = 691$, $p > 0.05$). Therefore, H₄: Institutional vulnerability is negatively correlated with teacher’s organisational commitment is failed to be supported. The results somewhat concur the previous findings (Akoto & Allida, 2017; Hosseini & Talebian Nia, 2015; Raman, Chang & Khalid, 2015; Reza, Jafar, Mohd., Hasan & Shahrookh, 2013), but deviate from the conceptual link between the two variables (Hoy, Tarter & Kottkamp, 1991).

The Influence of Organisational Climate on Teacher’s Organisational Commitment

Research question 4:

What is/are the dominant predictor factor/s of organisational climate on teacher’s organisational commitment?

Table 6: Correlation and Multiple Regression Analysis for Teacher’s Organisational Commitment on Predictor Variables

Predictor Variables	r	Standardized β Sig.	
Collegial leadership	0.66**	0.49**	0.00
Professional teacher behaviour	0.76**	0.58**	0.00
Achievement press	0.63**	0.45**	0.00
Institutional vulnerability	-0.12	-0.01	0.45
R ² = 0.66			
F = 13.142			
Adjusted R ² = 0.61			

**Significant at $p < 0.01$

a. Predictors: (Constant), Collegial leadership, Professional teacher Behaviour, Academic press.

b. Dependent Variable: Teacher’s organisational commitment

A multiple regression (Regression Enter Procedure) was administered to examine the individual influence of collegial leadership, professional teacher behaviour, achievement press and institutional vulnerability toward the teacher's organisational commitment. The four dimensions of organisational climate were entered as independent variables and teacher's organisational commitment as dependent variable. The results from Table 6 showed that the dimensions of organisational climate significantly predict the teacher commitment [$F(4, 686) = 13.142, p < 0.01$]. The combined influence of the organisational climate explained 61% of the variance change in teacher's organisational commitment (Adjusted $R^2 = 0.61, p < 0.01$). It is noteworthy that professional teacher behaviour was found to be the strongest predictor of teacher's organisational commitment ($\beta = 0.58, p < 0.01$). Collegial leadership ($\beta = 0.49, p < 0.01$) and achievement press ($\beta = 0.45, p < 0.01$) were also found as good predictors of teacher's organisational commitment. However, institutional vulnerability showed no significance to teacher's organisational commitment ($\beta = -0.01, p > 0.05$). This finding is somewhat deviated from the hypothesis H_5 : Professional teacher behaviour is the only predictor on teacher's organisational commitment. Therefore, H_5 is failed to be supported. The current study found that collegial leadership, professional teacher behaviour and achievement press were predictors of teacher's organisational commitment, instead of only one predictor for teacher's organisational commitment in the previous studies (Bahramia, et. al., 2016; Othman & Kasuma, 2016; Smith, 2009).

CONCLUSION AND IMPLICATIONS

The objective of this study was to examine the relationship of the four dimensions of organisational climate and teacher's organisational commitment within the context of the Sarawak vocational colleges. As

predicted, collegial leadership, professional teacher behaviour and achievement press showed positive relationship with teacher's organisational commitment. However, this study found that institutional vulnerability showed no significant relationship with teacher's organisational commitment.

The regression analysis in this study showed that there was a significant influence of organisational climate on teacher's organisational commitment. Furthermore, collegial leadership, professional teacher behaviour and achievement press were good predictors of teacher's organisational commitment with professional teacher behaviour being the best predictor. Institutional vulnerability was the only dimension in organisational climate which had no influence on teacher's organisational commitment.

The findings of this study supported some of the previous findings and confirmed that a significant relationship between the organisational climate and teacher's organisational commitment. Similar findings were determined in the current and previous studies. Firstly, the correlations performed in both studies found significant relationship between collegial leadership, professional teacher behaviour and achievement press and teacher's organisational commitment. Secondly, both studies also found that there was no relationship between institutional vulnerability and teacher's organisational commitment. Thirdly, both current and previous studies found that there was a significant influence of organisational climate on teacher's organisational commitment. Interestingly, one notable finding from the current study was that collegial leadership, professional teacher behaviour and achievement press were found to be the good predictors of teacher's organisational commitment. This finding is an added value to the existing literature and conceptual link on the

relationship between organisational climate and teacher's organisational commitment.

The results of this study have implications for vocational college, especially principals that are striving to foster teacher's organisational commitment. The conclusion made from this study is crucial for them on placing a major emphasis on professional teacher behaviour, collegial leadership and achievement press. Hence, a targeted professional development plan, provision of opportunities for shared decision making, cooperation and collaboration for both teachers and principal, besides setting higher and achievable academic standard within the college communities are all means to foster relationships of fellow teachers and the principal and eventually cultivate an open and healthy vocational college climate.

For further research, it is suggested to extend the sample to a wider scale to the teachers from vocational colleges nationwide. The results of the study could profitably be compared with the findings of the current study from the macro perspective. A future study might consider adding more independent variables such as the location of vocational college and its effects on collegial leadership, professional teacher behaviour, achievement press and commitment. The study might examine the relationship and the influence of location on organisational climate and teacher's organisational commitment. The study to examine the relationship between organisational climate and teacher's organisational commitment is arguably vital for the success of vocational colleges. The study of these variables will provide new insights and guidelines to vocational college administrators in particular and the Ministry of Education in their effort to cultivate conducive and healthy educational climate as well as to enhance higher level of commitment among

educators. Therefore, the importance of these two variables and others should be consistently and continually be tested and evaluated.

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